

NUMERICAL STUDY OF THE FORMATION OF LEAKAGE PATHS THROUGH CFRP LAMINATES FOR CRYOGENIC PROPELLANT TANKS

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ABSTRACT

Application of carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) to cryogenic fuel tank structures is expected to save structural weight of reusable launch vehicles. However, fuel leakage caused by the connection of matrix cracks in CFRP laminates under cryogenic environment is still a critical problem to be solved. The objective of this study is to develop and demonstrate the leak barrier layer made of thin-ply prepregs to prevent fuel leakage. In this study, the basic cryogenic mechanical properties of CFRP laminates were experimentally obtained and finite element models based on the data of cryogenic experiments were constructed. Finally, the influence of the difference of ambient temperature and the usefulness of the thin-ply barrier layer were numerically verified.

1 INTRODUCTION

Recently, application of composite materials to propellant tank structures has been studied in order to improve the performance of rockets by reducing weight. A large rocket consists of engines, cryogenic propellant tanks, a fairing and so on. The weight reduction of propellant tanks is expected to cause drastic weight saving of the rocket because the weight proportion of propellant tanks is specifically large. Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP), which have high specific strength as well as high specific stiffness and are widely used in aircraft structures are considered as promising material for reducing the weight of cryogenic propellant tanks (Fig. 1).

However, in 1990s, the results of the experiment of X-33 showed that multilayer matrix cracks in the CFRP laminate engendered detrimental fuel leakage (Fig. 2), and that it was necessary to study on tank structures from both leakage and damage tolerance perspectives [1]. The relationship between matrix cracks and permeability had been studied by researchers. Aoki et al. found that laminates could be damaged at lower stress level under cryogenic environment [2]. Furthermore, helium gas leakage through cross-ply laminates with matrix cracks was also investigated at room temperature (RT) by using cruciform specimens under biaxial loadings [3].

CFRP propellant tanks without liner were discussed in this study by considering that structural material itself should work as a barrier for the propellant leakage in space vehicles where weight saving is important. It was experimentally found that laminates using thin-ply prepregs had higher damage tolerance than that made of standard prepregs [4]. On the other hand, the results of the Composite Cryotank Technologies and Demonstration (CCTD) project that NASA and Boeing worked on were reported in 2015 [5]. They carried out pressure and thermal cycle tests, and succeeded in maintaining fuel for 2.4-m diameter and 5.5-m diameter composite tanks by using thin-ply prepregs. The current study focused on the method using thin-ply prepregs in order to prevent propellant leakage caused by the connection of matrix cracks. The aim of this study is to propose leak barrier layers using thin-ply prepregs and to numerically demonstrate their usefulness. Firstly, temperature dependence of

Figure 1: Overview of composite propellant tank [6]

Figure 2: Fuel leakage caused by the connection of matrix cracks.

material properties CFRP was obtained by cryogenic test. Secondly, analytical models were constructed based on the obtained data. Finally, the effectiveness of leak barrier layers was analytically determined.

This paper will explain the cryogenic experiments in Section 2. Finite element analyses (FEA) using experimental data are conducted in Section 3. The results of FEA and the effect of the presence of leak barrier layers on permeability of CFRP laminates are discussed in Section 4. Section 5 concludes the results of this paper.

2 EXPERIMENT

2.1 Coefficients of thermal expansion

In order to measure coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE) of CFRP under different ambient temperatures, experiments were carried out using unidirectional materials. Prepregs used in this experiment were T700SC/2500 from Toray and the thickness was about 0.06 mm per layer. The measurement instrument used in the experiment was DIL 402C/L180 from NETZSCH (Fig. 3). The measuring range of temperature was set from -170°C to 130°C . The temperature dependence of CTE in 0° and 90° directions was obtained.

Figure 3: DIL 402C/L180.

Figure 4: Temperature-dependent CTE of T700SC/2500.

As shown in Fig. 4, there is little temperature dependence in 0°-direction, but large temperature dependence is found in 90°-direction. It can be said that resin matrix has great temperature dependence and causes this tendency.

2.2 Elastic constants

Tensile tests using unidirectional CFRP were conducted in order to obtain the temperature dependence of elastic constants of T700SC/2500. For 0°-direction, biaxial test instrument from Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency was used. This instrument consisted of four hydraulic actuators arranged horizontally and refrigeration system as shown in Fig. 5. Thanks to the refrigeration system, material properties can be obtained not only at temperature of specific refrigerant, such as liquid hydrogen or liquid helium, but also at arbitrary temperature. The measuring ranges of temperature were set from -253°C to 20°C . For 90°-direction, the measuring instrument was INSTRON 8502 and the ranges of temperature were set from -150°C to 20°C .

As shown in Fig. 6, Young's moduli in 90°-direction, E_2 , and Poisson's ratio, ν_{12} , have high temperature dependence. As well as the results of CTE, these characteristics can be caused by temperature dependence of resin matrix.

Figure 5: Cryogenic testing instrument. (i) Overview of instrument.
(ii) Schematic of refrigeration system.

Figure 6: Temperature-dependent elastic constants of T700SC/2500.

3 FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

3.1 Outline

By using MSC. Marc 2013, FEA were carried out for two models: (a) not including leak barrier layers and (b) including leak barrier layers to verify damage resistance of leak barrier layers (Fig. 7).

Size of each model is $L 1 \text{ mm} \times W 1 \text{ mm}$ and the thickness of model (a) and (b) are 0.96 mm and 1.08 mm , respectively. The stacking sequence of each model and material properties of T700SC/2500 are shown in Table 1 and Table 2, respectively. Regarding other elastic constants and CTE, experimental data was used. Note that in this simulation, only the upper half of full model was considered because of the symmetricity of the stacking sequence. This can reduce the number of elements and calculation costs. The mesh was divided into 20 elements in the longitudinal, transverse and thickness directions per layer, and cracks were assumed to occur in the center of each layer.

Analyses consisted of two phases. In the first phase, ambient temperature decreased linearly from curing temperature. Then, biaxial strains were applied in the second phase. For each model, the formation of leakage paths caused by accumulation of matrix cracks was simulated.

Figure 7: Schematic of simulation models. (a) Laminate without thin-ply barrier layers. (b) Laminate with thin-ply barrier layers.

	Stacking sequence
(a)	$(0_4/90_4)_{2S}$
(b)	$(0_4/90_4/0_4/90_4/0/90)_S$

Table 1: Stacking sequence of finite element models.

Laminate properties	
In-plane shear modulus G_{12}	4.8 GPa
Out-of-plane shear modulus G_{23}	3.2 GPa
Out-of-plane shear modulus G_{31}	4.8 GPa
Out-of-plane Poisson's ratio ν_{23}	0.49
Interface properties	
Mode I maximum traction t_{IC}	60 MPa
Mode II and III maximum traction t_{IIC}	80 MPa
Mode I critical energy release rate G_{IC}	
Matrix crack	200 N/m
Delamination	100 N/m
Mode II and III critical energy release rate G_{IIC} and G_{IIIC}	
Matrix crack	800N/m
Delamination	400N/m

Table 2: Material properties of T700SC/2500.

3.2 Modeling of matrix crack and delamination

The cohesive zone model (CZM) approach [7] was used to present matrix cracks and delamination. It is one of the most popular approach to simulate interfacial fracture. This method relates tractions, \mathbf{t} , to relative displacement, δ , at an interface where a crack is assumed to occur.

The constitutive law used in this study is a bilinear relation between the tractions and the relative displacement. Cohesive finite elements were set in advance at the parts where matrix cracks and delamination were assumed to occur. As shown in Fig. 8, there is almost no relative displacement until the failure criteria defined by tractions is satisfied. This linear elastic part is defined using a penalty stiffness parameter, K , that ensures a stiff connection between surfaces of element discontinuity. When the failure criterion is satisfied, cohesive elements start to soften gradually. They are removed when they cannot transmit any traction. In this way, cohesive elements can assume onset and propagation of damage so that this method was used in numerical simulations of this study.

In the simulations, the failure criterion was defined by tractions as:

$$\left(\frac{t_I}{t_{IC}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{t_{II}}{t_{IIC}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{t_{III}}{t_{IIIC}}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (1)$$

and the crack propagation was defined by energy release rate as:

$$\left(\frac{G_I}{G_{IC}}\right)^\alpha + \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_{IIC}}\right)^\alpha + \left(\frac{G_{III}}{G_{IIIC}}\right)^\alpha = 1 \quad (2)$$

where subscript I, II and III show each fracture mode and subscript C indicates critical value. α is determined experimentally, and MSC. Marc 2013 uses $\alpha = 1.21$.

Figure 8: Traction-displacement curve of cohesive element.

3.3 Periodic boundary conditions

Considering that analytical models in this simulation were representative volume element (RVE) in a large structural component (Fig. 9), periodic boundary conditions that were proposed by Yoshida et al. [8] were given. Periodic boundary conditions applied to RVE shown in Fig. 10 are formulated as Eq. (3) to (7). First, for Face (A) and Face (C),

$$\begin{aligned} u_1(a, x_2, x_3) - u_1(-a, x_2, x_3) &= 2aE_{11} + 2ax_3K_{11} \\ u_2(a, x_2, x_3) - u_2(-a, x_2, x_3) &= 2aE_{12} + 2ax_3K_{12} \\ u_3(a, x_2, x_3) - u_3(-a, x_2, x_3) &= -2ax_2K_{12} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

and for Face (B) and Face (D),

$$\begin{aligned} u_1(x_1, b, x_3) - u_1(x_1, -b, x_3) &= 2bE_{12} + 2bx_3K_{12} \\ u_2(x_1, b, x_3) - u_2(x_1, -b, x_3) &= 2bE_{22} + 2bx_3K_{22} \\ u_3(x_1, b, x_3) - u_3(x_1, -b, x_3) &= -2bx_1K_{12} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Similarly, the conditions for Edge (a) and Edge (b) are given by

$$\begin{aligned} u_1(a, -b, x_3) - u_1(-a, -b, x_3) &= 2aE_{11} + 2ax_3K_{11} \\ u_2(a, -b, x_3) - u_2(-a, -b, x_3) &= 2aE_{12} + 2ax_3K_{12} \\ u_3(a, -b, x_3) - u_3(-a, -b, x_3) &= 2abK_{12} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

For Edge (a) and Edge (c),

$$\begin{aligned} u_1(a, b, x_3) - u_1(-a, -b, x_3) &= 2aE_{11} + 2bE_{12} + (2aK_{11} + 2bK_{12})x_3 \\ u_2(a, b, x_3) - u_2(-a, -b, x_3) &= 2aE_{12} + 2bE_{22} + (2aK_{12} + 2bK_{22})x_3 \\ u_3(a, b, x_3) - u_3(-a, -b, x_3) &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

and for Edge (a) and Edge (d),

$$\begin{aligned} u_1(-a, b, x_3) - u_1(-a, -b, x_3) &= 2bE_{12} + 2bx_3K_{12} \\ u_2(-a, b, x_3) - u_2(-a, -b, x_3) &= 2bE_{22} + 2bx_3K_{22} \\ u_3(-a, b, x_3) - u_3(-a, -b, x_3) &= 2abK_{12} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Note that u_i is the displacement of RVE in x_i ($i = 1, 2, 3$) direction and $E_{\alpha\beta}$, $K_{\alpha\beta}$ ($\alpha, \beta = 1, 2$) are macroscopic in-plane strain and macroscopic curvature, respectively.

Figure 9: Unit cell of a large structural component [8].

Figure 10: Definition of faces and edges of a unit cell [8].

3.4 Boundary conditions for symmetry in thickness direction

Due to the symmetry in the thickness direction of numerical models, only the upper half of the full models were considered in the FEA. The symmetry in the thickness direction was realized by giving following boundary conditions on the lower surface of the analytical models.

- 1) Displacement in thickness direction is 0.
- 2) Rotation in the direction perpendicular to the thickness direction is 0.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of FEA showed that the models of CFRP laminates were penetrated in the thickness direction by the accumulation of matrix cracks in each layer (Fig. 11).

For each model, the mechanism of the formation of leakage paths due to increased strain was different. Figure 12 shows the development of cracks for each laminate model under cryogenic temperature. In model (a): not including thin-ply barrier layers, a crack was generated in top 0° -layer which had the free edge firstly, and then the thickest 90° -layer began to be damaged. Finally, cracks in other layers were occurred and the leakage path was formed by connecting the cracks in all layers. On the other hand, in model (b): including thin-ply barrier layers, cracks in the thick layers were generated first, and then in the thinnest layer, a crack propagated from the boundary with the thick layer. Lastly, the leak path was formed. Considering such effect of thick layers, multiple thin-ply barrier layers are required to prevent leakage.

For each model, the strains at the formation of leakage path are shown in Fig. 13. Under the cryogenic temperature, leakage paths were generated in lower strain level than under RT for each model because of increased thermal stress. In addition, it can be found that the strain at the formation of the leakage path is higher for the laminate with thin-ply barrier layers.

5 CONCLUDING REMARKS

In this study, in order to confirm the usefulness of thin-ply barrier layers, material properties of CFRP under different ambient temperature were firstly obtained by cryogenic experiments. Next, finite element analyses using the experimental data were conducted for the two models of laminates: including thin-ply barrier layers and not including thin-ply barrier layers. The numerical results show that leakage paths can be generated at lower strain level under cryogenic temperature than under RT, and the strain at the formation of the leakage path was increased for the laminate with barrier layers. The results also show that considering effects of matrix cracks in thick layers, multiple thin-ply barrier layers is required to improve the leakage resistance of laminate.

As previously mentioned, the usefulness of thin-ply barrier layers for cryogenic propellant tank has been demonstrated numerically.

Figure 11: Connection of matrix cracks.

Figure 12: Development of matrix cracks in each model caused by increased biaxial strain under cryogenic temperature. (i) Propagation of cracks in 90° layers of each model. (ii) Propagation of cracks in 0° layers of each model.

Figure 13: Strain at the formation of leakage paths.

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